

Comparative Outcomes of Video-Associated Thoracoscopic Surgery and Open Thoracotomy in Lung Cancer Resection: A structured literature review

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Introduction

The surgical management of lung cancer resection is evolving from conventional open thoracotomy to minimally invasive procedures. Uniportal and Multiportal Video-Assisted Thoracoscopic Surgery (U-VATS and M-VATS) are widely used nowadays because they carry the potential to provide better perioperative and postoperative outcomes for lung cancer patients. Yet, their technical and oncological outcomes compared to open thoracotomy remain under debate. This review aims to compare and evaluate the techniques and outcomes of these surgical approaches.

Materials and methods

A Structured literature review was conducted from PubMed (2016-2026) using the keywords “open thoracotomy”, “surgery”, “multiportal VATS”, “uniportal VATS”, “lung cancer”. Studies were screened for relevance to comparative surgical outcomes. Meta-analyses, randomized controlled trials and observational studies were included. Articles that lacked comparative surgical outcomes or clinical relevance were excluded. Twenty-three relevant studies were selected and reviewed.

Results

Across the reviewed studies, VATS was associated with more favorable perioperative outcomes, including reduced wound infection rates, shorter hospital stay and lower intraoperative blood loss compared to open thoracotomy. Patients who underwent VATS experienced less acute and chronic postoperative pain and required shorter durations of epidural analgesia, although operating time was slightly longer. Oncological outcomes were generally comparable. Variations in nodal upstaging and long-term survival, were broadly comparable across surgical approaches. Reported differences should be cautiously interpreted due to potential selection bias. Within VATS approaches, U-VATS was associated with modest improvements in recovery and postoperative pain compared to M-VATS, with no clear difference in oncological outcomes.

Conclusion

VATS provides a more favorable perioperative and postoperative profile as compared to open thoracotomy with comparable oncological safety in appropriately selected patients. Oncological outcomes were influenced by disease stage, patient selection and surgical expertise. Further prospective studies are needed to strengthen the current evidence.

Keywords

Uniportal VATS, Multiportal VATS, Lung Cancer, Open Thoracotomy